

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF THE BOOK IN THE MODERN WORLD

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Abstract : Book of a person internal the world enriches This is life all stages important important owner , this is both an assistant , and a consultant , and entertainment . Books forever , but the Internet is forever it's not . Powers Internet and electricity off to put can People and country paralyzed will be , life stops . Whose if he has a " key " in his hand , that is the country to the hand in getting problem no . From the day to the day people book study stop are going - this while is a tragedy . Not only that people , maybe some of states their own governments state citizen for of the book importance does not understand.

The book enriches the inner world of a person. It is important in all stages of life, it is both a helper, an adviser and an entertainer. Books are forever, but the Internet is not. Powers can turn off the Internet and electricity. People and the country will be paralyzed, life will stop. Whoever has the "key" has no problem capturing such a country. From the day people stop reading books they are going - b u and it is a tragedy . Not only people, but also the governments of some countries do not understand the importance of the book for the citizen of their country. Analyzing the current situation in the world, we come to the conclusion that it is necessary and useful for someone. Nowadays, books are not as popular as they used to be. Modern people refuse to read books, they consider it a waste of time, especially for today's teenagers and young adults. Everyone is on social media. Unlike literature, the Internet and social networks do not teach anything good, they give ready-made correct answers easily and quickly. Literature teaches a person about life: it teaches him to understand, to observe, to search, to think. But most importantly, literature teaches us not to repeat the mistakes of others in our own lives. Books are needed to acquire new knowledge. Reading will increase your vocabulary. People who do not read books make many spelling mistakes . A person who reads develops a visual memory on the surface of words. Refusal to read is a recipe for difficulties in writing and speaking . Books according to their interests: someone likes detective stories, someone likes science fiction, someone likes fiction - prose, poetry, and someone

likes journalism. Either way, the person will get rich. The more it is, the more it will be enriched with new knowledge.

Books inspire and motivate many people to improve themselves and instill confidence in a person to achieve new goals in life. Passion for knowledge and books helps to become a smart person. Reading helps to discover new aspects, reveals previously unknown feelings and shades of perception of the world that we cannot imagine. In favor of reading, we can also cite the conclusions of many scientists who found that reading helps the human body stay young not only mentally, but also with physical health. Reading is beneficial for older adults for several reasons. First, the ability to translate words into mental forms and images has a positive effect on cognitive functions. Second, reading helps you focus. Therefore, reading books can be considered as a universal way to preserve consciousness even in old age.

It is important to understand that reading books expands your worldview and gives freedom to your imagination. But this book itself and its reading is only a small part of its impact on modern human life. Therefore, it is important to preserve the book as a basic value for future generations. Thanks to the libraries and the people who work there! Why should a modern person read a book? With the help of meaningful reading, new neural connections are formed in the brain of both adults and children, which help to think faster and improve memory. Why does a book improve a person? A person who has studied has more advantages in matters of public speaking and eloquence, because he feels more confident and can demonstrate higher knowledge. Reading aloud improves speech, enriches it with intonations, trains the voice and makes it pleasant to the ear. What happens to a person who reads a book? Reading improves brain function. Emory University scientists have proven that a person's intelligence level increases slightly within a few days after reading a book. According to the authors of the study, reading increases the number of neural connections in the human brain at a physiological level.

If you look at rich and successful people, you will see that most of them are constantly developing and reading books. And not just fiction books, but books on business, psychology, time management, success, relationships, and more. Some of them have their own home libraries. And what can you see by looking at the "poor" people who always complain about life? They go to work they don't like, they don't want to change anything, they don't want to learn new things, they don't read books, but there is a big TV at home, which they watch after work. Some students who enter universities relax and are welcomed to the best places to work immediately after

graduation, thinking that success and a happy life are guaranteed, and they only "show" their academic tasks. "for". Most often, textbooks taken from the library at the beginning of September lie in their rooms, unopened for the whole school year. Instead, phones, gadgets, computer games and various TV series grab their attention. We, the members of the older generation who grew up without computers and cell phones, are seeing the decline of some of today's youth. The Internet is a real addiction for some young people, taking up their valuable time and stunting their development. Scientists have long discovered how to maintain clarity of mind throughout life: you must constantly develop your brain. One of the best ways to do this is to read regularly and thoughtfully. Here are some more reasons why reading is beneficial .

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